

Deliverable 4.6: Joint International Scientific Conference VISION and International Network of Young Scientists Conference

(JISC&INYSC VISION)

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
Project type	Coordination and Supporting Action (CSA)
Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	R
Dissemination level	PU

Executive summary

This deliverable D4.6 is dedicated to the Joint International Scientific Conference VISION and International Network of Young Scientists Conference (JISC&INYSC). The idea behind JISC&INYSC was to summarize the VISION project's achievements, deepen collaboration between senior scientists, and build future cooperation among early-stage researchers. This event enabled the exchange of ideas, knowledge, and know-how, thus contributing to the creation of sustainable international networking and strengthening the innovation process. Moreover, this event was an excellent opportunity mainly for early-stage researchers and Ph.D. students to present and discuss their results in front of an international audience and reputable scientists, leading to encouraging them in their further work and enhancing their personal and professional development. An integral part of the conference was the VISION final project meeting, which was held in a hybrid form, allowing Dr. Doru Irimie, PO, from Brussels, Dr. Yvonne Kohl, the partner from Germany, and Prof. Nuria Malats, VISION Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) member, to participate in the meeting. Moreover, the social program of the conference enabled the participants to get closer to Slovakia's history, traditions, and nature.

1 Description of work & main achievements

The conference was held in the Slovak Academy of Sciences Congress Center, which is localized in Smolenice Castle, in Little Carpathians.

Fig. 1 The Congress Center of the Slovak Academy of Sciences

JISC&INYSC started on Monday, April 24, 2023, and ended on Thursday, April 27, 2023. The honorable guests of the JISC&INYSC conference, VISION SAB members, were Profs. Nuria Malats, Stefano Bonassi, and Andrew Collins. Moreover, Prof Silvia Pastorekova, the general director of the Biomedical Research Center of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, also accepted

the invitation to this scientific event. An integral part of this scientific event was VISION final project meeting. It was organized in a hybrid form to allow the participation of Dr. Doru Irimie, PO, from Brussels, and Dr. Yvonne Kohl, the partner from Germany, and Prof. Nuria Malats, VISION SAB member. For the conference purposes, a separate domain was created within the VISION website, where all relevant information relevant to this event was available (scientific program, social program, deadlines, templates for abstract and presentation, including registration).

1.1 Website of the conference

As the Congress Center in the Smolenice castle in Slovakia is located in a lovely place, the conference date was agreed upon among partners more than one year ahead. In January 2023, a website for the conference (http://vision.sav.sk/conference/index_conference.html) was created where all relevant information related to the conference (organizing committee, deadlines, reservation of accommodation, scientific and social program, templates for abstract and presentation, including online registration) was available. In addition, a Book of Abstracts from the conference had an ISBN.

Home

- Important notes
- Organizing Committee
- Registration & Accommodation Fees
- Call for abstracts
- Deadlines
- Program

Home

Joint International Scientific Conference VISION and International Network of Young Scientists Conference

The idea of this event is to encourage and facilitate mobility and direct contact between senior scientists and early-stage researchers to enable them to exchange ideas, knowledge, and information, thus building international networks and assisting the innovation process.

1.1.1 Conference materials

The organizing committee prepared for participants a cloth bag with conference materials (a notepad, a pen, a program, a badge, and a USB key with the Book of Abstracts) which they received at the registration. Each participant, including guests, also signed the list of participants (Annex 1).

All conference materials have the logo of the VISION project.

- The badge

Examples of badges

- The bag, the notepad with a pen, and the USB key

- The program of the conference

Monday, 24 April	
14:30 - 14:40	Welcome
14:40 - 15:15	A germline whole genome methylation score to predict pancreatic cancer risk / Nuria Malats
15:15 - 15:45	EATRIS: a key European distributed infrastructure for Translational Medicine / Laura Garcia Bermejo
15:45 - 16:15	Coffee break
16:15 - 16:45	Advancements in the understanding and targeting of pancreatic CSCs: from bench to pre-clinical models / Bruno Sains
16:45 - 17:15	Epigenetic inhibitors in the treatment of solid tumors / Bozena Smolkova
17:15 - 17:45	Experimental gene therapy mediated by extracellular vesicles in the treatment of PDAC / Marina Cibova
17:45 - 18:00	Nanocarrier-mediated multimodal anticancer therapy / Verona Buocikova
18:00 - 18:15	Development of orthotopic pancreatic PDX models / Maria Urbanova
18:15 - 19:15	Dinner
19:30	🇸🇰 VČELOVINA - tasting at family meadery
Tuesday, 25 April	
08:30 - 09:00	Role of hypoxia and acidosis in cancer progression / Silvia Pastorekova
09:05 - 09:30	Liquid Biopsy modalities in pancreatic cancer metastatic potential / Aagpi Kataki
09:30 - 09:45	Comprehensive analysis of Familial Pancreatic Cancer (FPC) suggests a different molecular subtype of patients with PDAC / Emma Barreto
09:45 - 10:00	Advanced in vitro models of pancreatic cancer / Lenka Trnkova
10:00 - 10:15	Mutational and Circulating Biomarkers Landscape in pNENS / Ioanna Anagnostouki
10:15 - 10:45	Coffee break
10:45 - 11:15	Circumventing chemoresistance in refractory tumors / Lucia Kucerova
11:15 - 11:45	Combinational therapy mediated by polyamidoamine dendrimers is efficient in colorectal cancer treatment / Miroslava Matuskova
11:45 - 12:00	Immunoprofiling of pancreatic tissue microenvironment in cancer patients / Alexandros-Georgios Tziagounis
12:00 - 12:15	PANGENFAM: The Spanish Familial Pancreatic Cancer Registry / Jorge Lopez Villalon
12:15 - 13:30	Lunch
13:30 - 13:50	The role of mitochondria in colorectal cancer cells – overexpression of mitofusin-2 changing mitochondrial dynamics / Silvia Tyciakova
13:50 - 14:10	Signaling pathways involved in metastasis / Lucia Demkova
14:10 - 14:30	DNA methylation changes in tumor progression / Viera Harvathova Kajibova
14:30 - 14:50	Gene editing of selective genes in gastrointestinal cell lines by CRISPR/Cas9 method / Zuzana Kotvasova
14:50 - 15:10	Genetic editing of ALDH1 stem cell marker isoforms is linked to distinct cellular and molecular properties in colorectal cell lines / Martina Poturnajova
15:10 - 15:25	Pancreatic lesions: The spectrum of syndecan-4 expression / Efthymios Koniaris
15:25 - 15:40	Surgical viewpoint of neoadjuvant therapy in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma / Peter Dubovan
15:40 - 16:10	Coffee break
16:10 - 16:40	Perioestin as a marker of chronic kidney disease progression / Andrea Babelova
16:40 - 17:10	Glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase nanoparticles: A promising novel therapy for ischemic stroke / Elise Runden-Piran
17:10 - 17:25	Animal models for gastrointestinal cancer / Katarina Gercakova
17:25 - 17:40	Effect of epigallocatechin gallate on the response of CRC-derived cells to chemotherapy / Nikoleta Moizesova
17:40 - 19:20	Dinner
19:30 - 22:30	🇸🇰 Majolika - Slovak folk pottery

<p>08:30 - 09:05</p> <p>09:05 - 09:35</p> <p>09:35 - 10:00</p> <p>10:00 - 11:30</p>	<p>A roadmap for translating early effects biomarker results into clinical practice: From observational studies to randomized controlled trials / Stefano Bonassi</p> <p>Recent updates in risk assessment of nanomaterials / Maria Dusinska</p> <p>Coffee break</p> <p>VISION final meeting</p>	<p>11:30 - 12:20</p> <p>16:00 - 16:30</p> <p>19:00</p>	<p>Wednesday, 26 April</p> <p>Lunch</p> <p>Refreshment</p> <p>Conference dinner</p>
<p>09:00 - 09:35</p> <p>09:35 - 09:55</p> <p>09:55 - 10:10</p> <p>10:10 - 10:25</p> <p>10:25 - 10:55</p> <p>10:55 - 11:25</p> <p>11:25 - 11:45</p> <p>11:45 - 12:00</p> <p>12:00 - 12:15</p>	<p>DNA damage and repair; possible predictors of cancer risk / Andrew Collins</p> <p><i>in silico</i> unravelling of descriptors for cytotoxicity and genotoxicity of nanomaterials to support hazard assessment and the S5BD approach / Noaouale El Yamani</p> <p>Human-induced pluripotent stem cell-derived alveolar epithelial cells as a promising cell source for in vitro lung models / Michelle Muller</p> <p>Biological safety of innovative nanocomposites with therapeutic potential / Lucia Balintova</p> <p>Coffee break</p> <p>Microfluidic platform for in vitro toxicity testing / Thorsten Knoll</p> <p>Hazard assessment of nanomaterials - meeting requirements for risk assessment / Eleonora Longhin</p> <p>What you can learn on training abroad / Kristina Jakic</p> <p>Analysis of tissue structural and functional changes following biodistribution and accumulation of 10 nm gold nanoparticles with BSA coating in mouse / Radka Macova</p>	<p>12:15 - 13:45</p> <p>13:45 - 14:05</p> <p>14:05 - 14:25</p> <p>14:25 - 14:45</p> <p>14:45 - 15:00</p> <p>15:00 - 15:20</p> <p>15:20 - 15:30</p> <p>15:30 - 16:00</p> <p>16:30</p>	<p>Thursday, 27 April</p> <p>Lunch</p> <p>Developing advanced blood-brain barrier models for pharmacological research / Karin Danz</p> <p><i>C. elegans</i> as a model system for assessing neurotoxicity / Tanima SenGupta</p> <p>Plate reader spectroscopy as an alternative to atomic absorption spectroscopy for the assessment of nanoparticle cellular uptake / Barbara Svitkova</p> <p>Comparison of the biological activity of <i>thymol</i> derivatives on 2D and 3D intestinal models / Michaela Blazickova</p> <p>Anti-fibrotic effects of <i>silvamarin</i> and <i>silvamarin</i>-coated gold nanoparticles against hepatic fibrosis in mouse / Michal Selc</p> <p>Closing the conference</p> <p>Refreshment</p> <p>Bus departure</p>

Wednesday, 26 April - Social Program:

Whole-day trip to **Little Carpathians**. "lunch-to-go" will be provided, departure at 10:00

Driny cave, departure at 12:30

JISC&INYS VISION
 April 24 -27, 2023
 Smolenice Castle, Slovakia

This project VISION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 857381

- The Book of Abstracts (Proceeding on the USB key)

1.2 The scientific program of the conference

The scientific program was prepared in close cooperation with the Steering Committee and Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) members. The program is available on the website (<http://vision.sav.sk/conference/program.html>). The conference started on Monday, 24, 2023, in the afternoon and finished on Thursday, 27, 2023, in the afternoon. The guests of the VISION conference were VISION SAB members, Profs. Nuria Malats, Stefano Bonassi, and Andrew Collins. Moreover, Prof. Silvia Pastorekova, DSc., the general director of the Biomedical Research Center, SAS, also accepted the invitation. All consortium partners contributed to the success of this event with their exciting presentations. As a result, the audience could listen to 42 fascinating talks, of which Ph.D. students gave 15. The main topics of the conference included pancreatic and colon cancer, tumor environment, cancer epigenetics, relevant *in vitro* 3D models, liquid biopsy, chemoresistance, cell signaling and editing, clinical trials, the biosafety of nanomaterials for medical use, the microfluidic system and potential cancer biomarkers.

The Book of Abstracts and presentations are available on the VISION website - http://vision.sav.sk/jisc_inysc_vision_conference.html.

All ready to start the conference

The conference's scientific program started with the online presentation given by Prof. Nuria Malats, VISION SAB member, who had to cancel her in-person attendance because she fell ill shortly before the conference started.

Prof. Nuria Malats

Then the scientific program continued with presentations given by senior scientists, young scientists (post-docs), and Ph.D. students from the hosting and partner organizations. After each talk, there was a space for discussion.

Experienced scientists, Ph.D. students, and young researchers (post-docs) – speakers and debaters, one joint scientific community

1.3 The social program of the conference

The aim of the social program prepared by the organizers was to acquaint the conference participants with local traditions, history, and the beauty of the surrounding nature of the Little Carpathians. On Monday evening, the participants visited the mead and honey craft excursion (Včelovina); on Tuesday, they had the opportunity to admire the beauty of Modra's pottery (Majolika), and on Wednesday, they visited the limestone Driny cave.

1.3.1 Vcelovina (Mead and honey craft excursion)

Vcelovina is a small company producing bee products (honey, wax, mead). Vcelovina, the first mead, results from lengthy honey experiments. The sophisticated taste of mead is achieved by using different types of honey and herbs.

The excursion to Vcelovina

1.3.2 Majolika (Ceramics manufacture excursion)

The process of majolika production follows the centuries-old traditions of the pottery craft in Modra. All products are handmade and painted. Each piece is a unique work of art. The Modra's majolika and ornamentation are registered in Slovakia's Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

The excursion to Majolika

To commemorate the JISC & INYSC VISION conference and the VISION project, each participant received a small gift.

A small vase from Majolika

1.3.3 Trips to Male Karpaty (Little Carpathians)

- Hiking to the highest peak in the Little Carpathians – Záruby

Zaruby is the highest hill of the Little Carpathians. Due to bad weather (rain and snow), this hiking tour was officially canceled. Only a couple of young Ph.D. students were not deterred by the weather and went to Zaruby.

Beautiful view from the peak of Zaruby

Molpír Hillfort

- Walking trip to Driny cave

Most participants visited the Driny cave – the only cave open to the public in Western Slovakia, close to the Smolenice castle. Characteristic sinter curtains with serrated edging are typical for the cave. There are also sinter lakes, waterfalls and flows, pagoda stalagmites, and various stalactites. The visitors could also admire the bats – the stable inhabitants of the cave.

Before entering the Driny cave

On Wednesday, the farewell conference dinner took place. After the dinner, there was a good opportunity for an informal discussion about potential cooperation in the future and dance.

1.4 The VISION final project meeting

As part of the conference, the final VISION meeting took place on Wednesday, April 26, 2023, in a hybrid form. Dr. Doru-Leonard Irimie, the Project Officer, Prof. Alfredo Carrato (previous Steering Committee member), Dr. Yvonne Kohl, and Prof. Nuria Malats attended this meeting via online mode.

The minutes and the list of participants from this VISION final project meeting are available in a deliverable D1.2 Kick-off and consortium regular meeting minutes.

- Agenda of the meeting

AGENDA

10:00 – 11:30 **Welcome and overview of project objectives and structure**

Dissemination and Exploitation plan update

Summary of what was done: training activities, invited lectures, online courses, project proposals, Ph.D. students – defense of the thesis, publications, presentations, website update, outreach activities, conferences

Assessment of applications for training events.

Project management

The timeframe of deliverables, responsible partners

Preparation for the Final Technical and Financial Report

Any other business

Wrap up and close the meeting

- Participants of the final meeting

Participants in the Smolenice castle

Online participants

2 Deviation from the workplan

This scientific event was held as initially planned in the project proposal. Therefore, there was no deviation from the workprogram.

3 Conclusion

Nearly 50 participants from all consortium partners attended the conference. Despite the cold weather, the atmosphere of this scientific meeting was enjoyable and friendly. The coffee breaks and social program were good opportunities for informal discussions on how to further cooperate after the end of the VISION project.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

Participants of the JISC&INYSC conference (VISION family)

ANNEX 1: List of participants

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The participant of the event hereby grants his/her consent with photographing of the event (without any consideration) and consents with the publishing of such recordings, including the images of participants, on the websites, in the media and in any promotional materials, for the purpose of informing the public of the event and presenting the activities of VISION project. He/She also agrees with collecting, preservation and processing of personal data for the implementation of VISION project.

Name	Organization	April 24, 2023	April 25, 2023	April 26, 2023	April 27, 2023
Ioanna ANGELIOUDAKI	NKUA				
Andrea BABELOVA	BMC SAV				
Lucia BALINTOVA	BMC SAV				
Emma BARRETO MELIAN	IRYCIS				
Michaela BLAZICKOVA	BMC SAV				
Stefano BONASSI	IRCCS SAN RAFFAELE ROMA				
Verona BUOCIKOVA	BMC SAV				
Martin BYSTRIANSKY	ÚRAD SAV				
Maria CIHOVA	BMC SAV				

List of participants

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Name	Organization	April 24, 2023	April 25, 2023	April 26, 2023	April 27, 2023
Andrew COLLINS	UNIVERSITY OF OSLO				
Karin DANZ	FRAUNHOFER IBMT				
Lucia DEMKOVA	BMC SAV				
Peter DUBOVAN	BMC SAV				
Maria DUSINSKA	NILU				
Elisabeth ELJE	NILU				
Alena GABELOVA	BMC SAV				
Laura GARCIA BERMEJO	IRYCIS				
Katarina GERCAKOVA	BMC SAV				

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Name	Organization	April 24, 2023	April 25, 2023	April 26, 2023	April 27, 2023
Viera HORVATHOVA KAJABOVA	BMC SAV				
Agapi KATAKI	NKUA				
Thorsten KNOLL	FRAUNHOFER IBMT				
Efthymios KONIARIS	GENERAL HOSPITAL OF ATHENS				
Katarina KOZICS	BMC SAV				
Zuzana KOZOVSKA	BMC SAV				
Lucia KUCEROVA	BMC SAV				
Eleonora Marta LONGHIN	NILU				
Radka MACOVA	BMC SAV				

List of participants

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Name	Organization	April 24, 2023	April 25, 2023	April 26, 2023	April 27, 2023
Nuria MALATS	CNIO				
Miroslava MATUSKOVA	BMC SAV				
Nikoleta MOJZESOVA	BMC SAV				
Michelle MULLER	FRAUNHOFER IBMT				
Silvia PASTOREKOVA	BMC SAV				
Martina POTURNAJOVA	BMC SAV				
Elise RUNDEN-PRAN	NILU				
Bruno SAINZ	IRYCIS				
Michal SELC	BMC SAV				

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Name	Organization	April 24, 2023	April 25, 2023	April 26, 2023	April 27, 2023
Tanima SENGUPTA	NILU				
Tatiana SIPOSOVA	BMC SAV				
Bozena SMOLKOVA	BMC SAV				
Monika SRAMKOVA	BMC SAV				
Barbora SVITKOVA	BMC SAV				
Lenka TRNKOVA	BMC SAV				
Silvia TYCIAKOVA	BMC SAV				
Alexandros-Georgios TZIGOUNIS	NKUA				
Jorge VILLALON LOPEZ	IRYCIS				

List of participants

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Name	Organization	April 24, 2023	April 25, 2023	April 26, 2023	April 27, 2023
Maria URBANOVA	BMC SAV				
Julie EARL	IRYCIS				
Silvia GONZALÉZ MARTINEZ	IRYCIS				

